

WORKING MOTHERS IN NON-PROFIT SECTORS IN MYANMAR: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY ON ACHIEVING WORK-LIFE BALANCE

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Abstract

This study aims to evaluate the effect of work-life balance on the job performance of working mothers in non-profit sectors in Myanmar, identifying the crucial factors that support work-life balance with regards to family background and the work environment. A 5-point Likert scale was used to conduct quantitative research and measure satisfaction with work-life balance. The study assesses overall satisfaction in terms of personal, balancing, organizational, motivational, career advancement, and psychological factors, using descriptive and analytical methods. Our findings indicate that despite negative psychological and career advancement factors, working mothers in non-profit sectors are satisfied with organizational support and motivation from the work environment and family, and make efforts to adjust their work-life balance. We highlight the importance of work-life balance, with its immense influence on the employee and the organization. Our research contributes to the ever-expanding literature on work-life balance and its implications for various sectors in Myanmar. Our survey, which utilized a self-designed questionnaire distributed among 208 working mothers in non-profit sectors in Yangon, Myanmar, identified six essential dimensions of work-life balance: personal, balancing, organizational, motivational, career advancement, and psychological factors. Improving work-life balance in working mothers by considering these factors will lead to a better job performance.

Keywords: Working Mothers, Work-Life Balance, Maslow's Theory, Personal Factors, Balancing Factors, Organizational Factors, Motivational Factors, Career Advancement Factors, and Psychological Factors.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The growing trend of working mothers in today's world has highlighted the need for a better work-life balance. The new Work-Life Balance directive, introduced in 2019, aims to provide workers with the necessary rights to achieve better work-life balance (*Tajani, 2019*). However, finding a balance between the roles of modern women and working mothers remains a difficult task, as working mothers try to balance their careers with their family responsibilities (*Ladge, 2015*). Women's roles in the workforce have evolved significantly, with a paradigm shift from traditional gender roles to women becoming both breadwinners and capable of handling multiple roles (*Green, 2015*). This juggling act often leads to mothers attempting to 'do it all' and internalizing motherhood's

unreasonable expectations, leading to stress and an inability to balance parenting and work responsibilities (*Pare, 2016*).

Good work-life balance is vital for organizational success, leading to higher productivity and employee performance (*Sumaiti, 2016; Wolor et al., 2020*). However, work-life balance is a challenge for everyone, particularly women employees, including working mothers. The simultaneous pursuit of career and motherhood goals is often daunting due to conflicting role expectations and demands, leading to stress and pressure on working mothers (*Toffoletti & Starr, 2016; Gragnano, Simbula, & Miglioretti, 2020*). Despite these challenges, organizations are stepping up to provide better work-life balance policies to retain a talented workforce (*TEKLU, 2020*).

In Myanmar, some women lawyers struggle to maintain a work-life balance due to family obligations. While single women have more flexibility in this regard, married women lawyers have to juggle multiple responsibilities, including their husbands' demands and managing their children's educational affairs (*Perez E. & Pwint WWS, 2021*). Achieving a work-life balance is crucial to improve employee productivity, ensure a healthy work environment, and maintain organizational success.

This research analyzes the impact of work-life balance on the job performance of working mothers in non-profit organizations in Yangon regions, Myanmar. Working mothers face difficulties in managing their personal lives and family responsibilities due to the increasing burden of work. Poor work-life balance can lead to health deterioration, strained relationships, and decreased productivity, resulting in absenteeism, low morale, and high employee turnover. This study aims to assess the work-life balance of working mothers in non-profit sectors and identify factors contributing to an imbalance. The significance of this research lies in providing insight into work-life balance issues that can help organizations retain employees, increase productivity, and encourage optimum working hours. The findings of this study suggest solutions to improve the productivity and well-being of working mothers in non-profit organizations in Yangon regions, Myanmar.

In this study on the work-life balance of working mothers in non-profit organizations in Yangon, limitations included low response rates and a convenience sample that limited generalizability. Additionally, the study faced challenges such as the Myanmar military coup in 2021 and the COVID-19 outbreak, which impacted data collection. Despite these limitations, the study provided valuable insights into how working mothers manage their work and life and the impact of work-life balance on their performance. Future research should continue to explore this topic and address limitations such as testing the reliability and validity of research instruments.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Working mothers are defined as women who work outside of their home for income while fulfilling their maternal duties at home (*Tripathi & Randev, 2016*). Work-life balance has become a crucial topic in today's world with many studies exploring the causes and consequences of work-life imbalance. *Tasnim, Hossain, & Enam (2017)* define work-life balance as effectively combining professional and personal obligations to create harmony between the two aspects of life. However, work-life imbalance can have negative consequences for both the employee and employer. Personal factors such as personal happiness and well-being, sufficient time for personal hobbies and interests, and balancing personal and work life can support working mothers in achieving work-life balance. These factors impact enthusiasm, motivation, and efficiency in the workplace. Women who juggle children and household responsibilities may feel overwhelmed, both physically and mentally, and must prioritize self-care activities such as spending time with friends or family, going on a quick getaway, or engaging in hobbies (*Tasnim, Hossain, & Enam, 2017*).

Balancing factors, organizational factors, and motivational factors are all important when it comes to achieving work-life balance. According to *Brue (2019)*, balancing factors refer to elements that enable individuals to balance work and personal life, such as time management, spending quality time with family, and recognizing organizational policies. Additionally, *Sangarandeniya (2020)* emphasizes the importance of strong work-life balance practices for attracting and retaining talented employees and reducing turnover costs. Organizational factors, such as maternity leave support and flexible working arrangements, are also crucial for achieving work-life balance (*Nasscom, 2016; Chaitra, Ashok Kumar, & Renuka Murthy, 2016*). Finally, motivational factors, such as family support, childcare provisions, and passion for work, can also contribute to work-life balance (*Maslow, 1943*).

Research shows that both men and women experience organizational stress, but there is a common recognition that women across cultures face a greater level of stress than men. Working women, in particular, experience higher levels of stress than men due to the multiple roles they often play at home in addition to their work responsibilities. These roles can include caring for husbands, children, or elderly parents, while still striving for success in the workplace and working towards achieving personal and professional goals (*Perez E. F., et al 2023*).

Saraswati R, Perez, EF, et al. (2023) conducted research on women's stress, and the results suggest that there are several factors that can contribute to higher stress levels for businesswomen, such as motivated performance. However, it is important to emphasize the importance of work-life balance to reduce stress levels for female employees. The study found that both Type A and Type B personalities had average stress levels in several workplace stressors. Therefore, organizations can focus on improving work-life balance by offering flexible work arrangements and support for employees' personal lives. *Swathi and Reddy (2016)* also suggest that high stress levels

in the workplace are a growing trend among women, and addressing this issue is critical for improving overall well-being and job satisfaction.

However, there are both positive and negative consequences of work-life balance and imbalance. While work-life balance can boost motivation and job satisfaction, work-life imbalance can lead to stress, burnout, and psychological strain (*Phipps & Prieto, 2016*). It is important for organizations and individuals to prioritize work-life balance to promote overall employee well-being and productivity.

Physiological needs, safety needs, social needs, esteem needs, self-actualization needs, career advancement, and psychological factors are all important factors that impact work-life balance. Employers can support employees' physiological needs by providing comfortable working conditions, reasonable work hours, and necessary breaks (*Hawke, 2017*).

According to Maslow's hierarchy of needs, employees also have safety needs, including job security and protection from accidents and harm (*Maslow, 1943*). Social needs, including the need for a sense of belonging and acceptance, can be fulfilled through promoting teamwork and a positive work environment (*Hawke, 2017*).

Additionally, meeting employees' esteem needs through recognition and promotion opportunities can contribute to job satisfaction (*Maslow, 1943*).

Self-actualization needs, such as the desire to reach one's full potential, can be fulfilled through challenging work and autonomy (*Hawke, 2017*).

Discrimination against women, both during recruitment and after childbirth, can hinder career advancement and negatively impact work-life balance (*Kumar & Shaema, 2018*).

Psychological factors such as increased workload and burnout must be addressed by employers to prevent negative physical and mental health consequences for employees (*Kohll, 2018*). Employers should strive to improve the overall workplace experience for their employees to support work-life balance (*Hawke, 2017*).

Work-life balance is no longer limited to the traditional concepts of work and personal life and has evolved into a beneficial state of mind for individuals. In its broadest sense, work-life balance is defined as a satisfactory level of involvement or 'fit' between the multiple roles in a person's life (*Mugambi, 2019*). This includes the interaction between paid work, unpaid work in families and communities, personal development, and enjoyment (*Gragnano, Simbula, & Miglioretti, 2020*). According to Gragnano et al., work-life balance also involves an individual's perception of compatibility between work and non-work activities and growth aligned with their current life priorities. Recent research has shown that a better work-life balance leads to job satisfaction, job performance, organizational commitment as well as life and family satisfaction. Moreover, achieving work-life balance has been found to reduce adverse psychological outcomes such as psychological distress, emotional exhaustion, anxiety, and depression (*Gragnano et al., 2020*).

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study design involves various components, including data collection, sampling, questionnaire design, and conceptual framework. The current study examines the impact of work-life balance on job performance among working mothers, utilizing a mixed-methods approach, consisting of probability and non-probability sampling techniques for both quantitative and qualitative data (Patten, 2018). The structured questionnaire focuses on personal, balancing, organizational, motivational, career advancement, and psychological factors that impact work-life balance (Nisar, Hafeez, & Raza, 2020). Basic random sampling is utilized to statistically analyze the gathered data. Qualitative research is exploratory, seeking to understand the possible causes of issues through observation, behavior analysis, and verbal data. To ensure a balance of data, the study conducts a structured systematic review based on qualitative research methods, consisting of developing research questions, literature searches, article selection, analysis and synthesis of qualitative findings, quality control, and reporting (Wolar et al., 2020). The interpretation of quantitative research results can be consistent across various experts, while qualitative research may vary based on the observer's skill.

4.0 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

After reviewing the previous studies, the researchers have established the following figure-conceptual structure. The study was conducted using descriptive survey design. The framework shows that adequate work-life balance of Non-Profit sectors working mothers would effectively have a positive impact on job performance of working mothers. Negative impact is a major reason for the imbalance of work life balance of working mothers. Work-life balance is an overall determinant of employee performance in non-profits governmental organizations and work-life imbalance affects low performance of employees to the organization. The study recommended that employee work-life balance has a very big impact on employees clearly indicating conditions upon.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of Work-Life Balance Source: (Farandole, 2013)

5.0 ANALYSIS OF FINDINGS

All the primary data was analyzed through numerical analysis. The quantitative data gathered about the working mothers in Non-Profit sectors in the Yangon Region of Myanmar was reliable data and analyzed using the descriptive approach.

The findings were described through descriptive statistics, presenting frequency tables and pie charts. To evaluate the relationship between work-life balance and job performance in the Non-Profit sectors for working mothers, the author assessed the level of influencing factors, including personal factors, balancing factors, organizational support, motivational support, career advancement, and psychological factors. Regression analysis was used to determine the relationship between the variables (*Tin, 2020*).

In this section, the empirical findings of the study were analyzed using primary data and secondary information to demonstrate the contribution of the research in the field of work-life balance of working mothers, as provided by the investigation of Non-profit sector organizations. The study set a foundation for examining the impact of work-life balance on job performance by drawing upon previous literature.

The findings presented in the study highlighted that work-life balance was measured upon personal factors, balancing factors, organizational factors, motivational factors, career advancement, and psychological impact on working mothers' work-life balance (*Jamaludin, Sulaiman, & Hashim, 2015*).

5.1 Demographic Profile of Respondents

In order to gather information about working mothers in Non-profit Organizations (INGO, LNGO and UN), a questionnaire was designed including questions about their age, marital status, number of children, occupation, specialized professional background, monthly income, years of working experience, specialization studied area, and reason for studying. A total of 208 questionnaires were collected from 208 working mothers in Non-profit organizations, with a response rate of 100%.

The combined demographic profiles of the respondents are presented in Annexure 2. The *age distribution* in years of the respondents was as follows: 25-34 age group with 52 respondents representing 25%, 35-44 age group with 132 respondents representing 63%, 45-54 age group with 20 respondents representing 10%, and above 55 age group with 4 respondents representing 2%.

Figure 2: Age

According to the data obtained from the survey, out of the 208 respondents, 4% (n=8) reported having a traditional married life, while the majority of respondents (n=164, 79%) reported being in a married life with full support from their family. A significant minority of respondents (n=32, 15%) reported being married life with a long-distance relationship with their spouse. The remaining 2% of respondents (n=4) reported being a single mother without support from extended family.

Figure 3: Marital Status of Respondents

Out of the 208 respondents, 9% (n=19) reported having one child, while the majority of respondents (n=81, 39%) reported having two children. A significant percentage of respondents (n=108, 52%) reported having three or more children.

Figure 4: Number of Children of Respondents

Organization of respondents -Out of 208 respondents, 40 respondents working at INGO representing 19%, 12 respondents who worked at LNGO representing 6%, 156 respondents who worked at UN representing 75% respectively.

Figure 5: Organization of Respondents

According to the survey data, out of the 208 respondents, 19% (n=40) reported being program staff involved in program management, operations, and M&E data management, among others. The majority of respondents (n=168, 81%) reported being support service staff involved in administrative, HR, finance, ICT, logistics, and related sectors.

Figure 6: Professional Sectors of Respondents

Based on the survey of 208 respondents, only a small percentage (n=4, 2%) reported earning less than 500,000 MMK per month. A larger percentage (n=20, 10%) reported earning between 500,000 and 1,000,000 MMK per month. The majority of respondents (n=64, 31%) reported earning between 1,000,000 and 2,000,000 MMK per month. A significant number of respondents (n=100, 48%) reported earning between 2,000,000 and 3,000,000 MMK per month, while a minority of respondents (n=20, 10%) reported earnings above 3,000,000 MMK per month.

Figure 7: Monthly salary of the Respondents

From analyzing the survey responses of 208 participants, it was apparent that most respondents (n=116, 56%) had accumulated over 5 years of work experience. Subsequently, a sizable number of participants (n=44, 21%) reported possessing 3-5 years of work experience, while an equivalent number of respondents (n=44, 21%) had 1-3 years of work experience. The minority of respondents (n=2, 2%) had less than 1 year of work experience.

Figure 8: Working Experiences of Respondents

Regarding the query "Does the work-life balance significantly affect the job performance of working mothers?" it was observed that 192 out of 208 respondents (92%) answered affirmatively, while only 18 out of 208 (8%) responded negatively.

Figure 9: Work-life balance impact to working mother's Job Performance

Figure 10: Relationship between WLB Job performances

5.2 Discussion on Descriptive Statistics of Working Mothers Work-Life Balance

The following are discussions on each of the parameters of working mothers work –life balance; refer to Annexure 3 for actual statistics:

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Work-Life Balance

Descriptive Statistics of Work-life Balance					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Personal factor	208	1.00	4.75	3.2404	0.78168
Balancing factor	208	1.00	4.17	3.4231	0.58379
Organization factor	208	1.00	5.00	3.6593	0.94913
Motivation factor	208	1.00	5.00	3.8846	0.72960
Career Advancement	208	1.00	5.00	3.5048	0.69067
Psychological factor	208	1.00	5.00	3.5154	0.60189
Valid N (listwise)	208				

1= strongly disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Neutral, 4= Agree, 5= Strongly Agree

The personal factor was deemed critical, as indicated by the mean index score surpassing three, and over 50% of respondents rating 3=Neutral and 4=Satisfied. This factor is essential for women, as it emphasizes the need to focus on self-care before taking care of others. It highlights the significance of "Me" time as it offers an opportunity for mothers to rejuvenate and heal, away from domestic and work-related stresses.

Similarly, the balance factor was also deemed critical, with a mean index score exceeding three, and over 50% of respondents rating 3=Neutral and 4=Satisfied. Respondents highlighted the challenge of balancing work and family life and appreciated the flexible working hours and supportive work environment of non-profit organizations.

The organizational factor was also considered critical, with a mean index score above three, and over 50% of respondents rating 3=Neutral and 4=Satisfied. The respondents emphasized the importance of organizational support, which includes benefits and rewards, non-discrimination, flexible working hours, and annual leave.

The motivational factor was also critical, with a mean index score surpassing three, and more than 50% of respondents rating 3=Neutral and 4=Satisfied. This factor refers to how personal passion and pride in one's job motivate working mothers. Respondents appreciated having a comfortable and safe working environment that provides financial assistance for personal use, support from supervisors, colleagues at work, and family members at home.

Career advancement was highlighted as another critical factor, with a mean index score exceeding three and over 50% of respondents rating 3=Neutral and 4=Satisfied. This factor emphasizes the importance of organizational support, such as training and personal development, equal promotion opportunities, and learning opportunities in one's respective career job.

Finally, the psychological factor was also considered critical, with a mean index score above three, and over 50% of respondents rating 3=Neutral and 4=Satisfied. The psychological factor concerns the support of a spouse for handling dual roles at home, where flexible working hours can significantly reduce stress levels. Respondents noted that working mothers who receive family support are more comfortable than those who do not in their current dual role.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of PBOMCP

Descriptive Statistics of PBOMCP					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Personal factor	208	1.00	4.75	3.2404	0.78168
Balancing factor	208	1.00	4.17	3.4231	0.58379
Organization factor	208	1.00	5.00	3.6593	0.94913
Motivation factor	208	1.00	5.00	3.8846	0.72960
Career Advancement	208	1.00	5.00	3.5048	0.69067
Psychological factor	208	1.00	5.00	3.5154	0.60189
PBOMCP_factors	208	1.04	4.54	3.5379	0.56298
Valid N (listwise)	208				

The PBOMCP analysis revealed that the mean score for the motivational factor had the highest value of 3.8846 with a standard deviation of 0.72960. On the other hand, the mean score for the organizational factor had the lowest value of 3.6593 with a standard deviation of 0.94913, while the mean psychological factor score was 3.5154 with a standard deviation of 0.60189.

The mean scores for career advancement and psychological factors were slightly lower than the overall PBOMCP mean of 3.5379. In contrast, personal and balancing factors had mean scores below the overall mean of PBOMCP. The mean score for personal factors was the lowest at 3.2404, with a standard deviation of 0.78168.

These results highlight that the contribution of motivational factors to working mothers' work-life balance is higher than anticipated, as reflected by the highest mean score among the factors.

Table 3: Pearson's Correlation of 'Satisfaction Score' with PBOMCP

Satisfied_or_not	Persona l factor	Balancing factor	Organization factor	Motivation factor	Career Advancement	Psychological factor	
Pearson Correlation	1	0.059	0.046	.195**	.181**	0.073	0.079
Sig. (2-tailed)		0.400	0.513	0.005	0.009	0.009	0.257
N	208	208	208	208	208	208	208

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation table presented below indicates a significant positive correlation (at $P=0.01$) between the dependent construct's variables, which include "Personal factors," "Balancing factors," "Organizational factors," "Motivational factors," "Career Advancement," and "Psychological factors". The correlation coefficient between "satisfaction score" and "Organizational score" is the highest ($r = 0.195$), indicating that organizational support and initiatives for implementing work-life balance policies, such as workshops, paid maternity leave programs, flexible working hours, non-discriminatory practices, and support for staff and family, have a positive impact on employee satisfaction.

Conversely, the correlation coefficient between "satisfaction score" and "Balancing factors" is the lowest ($r = 0.046$), implying that some working mothers face challenges regarding work-life balance, depending on their work nature, professional background, working hours, marital status, and family support. Balancing work, family commitments, and personal well-being can be particularly challenging for working mothers without supportive partners. Hence, there is a need to investigate the cause-effect relationship between the constructs using a regression model.

To determine the “work-life balance for working mothers' ' score, we calculated the mean of the factors and assigned values above the mean satisfaction score. Conversely, scores below the mean satisfaction were categorized as “work-life unbalance for working mothers.” Based on this dichotomous outcome variable, the cause-and-effect relationship between independent constructs variables (PBOMCP) and “work-life balance” was studied using binary logistic regression in SPSS (version 25.0).

5.4 Binomial Logistic Regression Analysis

- i) Dependent variable: work-life balance =recommended (Value “0” = low level of satisfaction and “1” =high level of satisfaction).

Table 4: Binomial Logistic Regression Analysis of PBOMCP

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Personal factor	0.039	0.419	0.009	1	0.925	1.040	0.457	2.366
Balancing factor	-0.883	0.674	1.718	1	0.190	0.414	0.110	1.549
Organization factor	0.649	0.435	2.224	1	0.136	1.914	0.815	4.494
Motivation factor	1.097	0.775	2.007	1	0.157	2.996	0.656	13.674
Career Advancement	-0.307	0.488	0.395	1	0.530	0.736	0.283	1.914
Psychological factor	-0.470	0.853	0.304	1	0.581	0.625	0.117	3.324
Constant	1.513	1.446	1.094	1	0.296	4.539		

a. Variable(s) entered on step 1: Q17_Personalfactor, Q18_balancingfactor, Q19_organizationfactor, Q20 Motivationfactor, Q21 CareerAdvancement, Q22 Psychologicalfactor.

The Wald test results, displayed in the “Wald” column, determine the statistical significance of each independent variable. The “Sig.” column displays the significance of the test. The results indicate that only Organizational factors (at $p = 2.2$) contribute significantly to the model/prediction. The odds ratio, presented in the Exp (B) column, shows that an increase in motivational factors scores by one unit increases the probability of working mothers feeling a high level of work-life satisfaction by 2.996 times in the same direction. The confidence interval for motivational factors ranges from 0.656 to 13.674, which suggests that reliability is between 0.656 to 13.674 times more likely to make working mothers feel highly satisfied with their work-life balance than dissatisfaction. This variable has a higher confidence interval compared to the others as it is the only variable that is significant, indicating its explanatory power over the others.

The regression coefficient (B) of Personal factors, Organizational factors, and Motivational factors are positive, suggesting their positive relationship with working mothers' work-life balance satisfaction. In contrast, Balancing factors, Career advancement, and psychological factors have negative regression coefficient (B) and odds ratio less than one, indicating their negative relationship with satisfaction.

6.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Conclusion

The concept of Work-Life Balance is a crucial aspect of Human Resource Management that holds a significant impact on employee performance and productivity. This study aims to evaluate the level of work-life balance among working mothers from various professional backgrounds in non-profit organizations. The study assesses several factors, such as **Personal factors, Balancing factors, Organizational factors, Motivational factors, Career Advancement, and Psychological factors (PBOMCP)**.

The analysis of data responses indicates that most working mothers are satisfied with their life as they are motivated to manage their dual roles and receive adequate support from their organization. However, the **lower scores in Balancing factors and Personal factors** suggest the need for improvements in managing work and family responsibilities and allocating time for personal well-being.

The positive correlation coefficient between satisfaction and constructs/variables PBOMCP indicates that enhancing these variables can positively impact working mothers' work-life balance. Among these variables, **Motivational factors, Organizational factors, and Psychological factors** play a crucial role in improving work-life balance for working mothers.

Further, the study provides a comprehensive overview of the level of work-life balance among working mothers, highlighting the importance of prioritizing this issue for the betterment of employees' well-being and organizational productivity.

This study identifies **six primary findings**:

1. Some working mothers need more personal time for their interests and wellbeing.
2. Some working women still struggle to balance work and family responsibilities.
3. Organizational support in non-profit organizations significantly benefits working mothers' work-life balance through various policies.
4. Working mothers show dedication to their job, feel comfortable in a supportive environment, and have positive relationships with colleagues.
5. Career development support is lacking for some working mothers.
6. Working mothers have moderate ability in handling domestic pressures and stress at work while receiving support from spouses.

The importance of work-life balance for job performance, employee well-being, and organizational commitment is a well-established concept, supported by numerous studies (*Thevanes, N. & Mangaleswaran.T, 2018; Kerdpitak & Jermsttiparsert, 2020*). A balanced work-life can lead to higher motivation, job satisfaction, productivity, and overall better performance. Conversely, employees who experience an imbalance may suffer from negative health consequences, lower productivity, and increased turnover rates,

affecting overall productivity. Therefore, organizations must prioritize initiatives that promote work-life balance to enhance motivation, productivity, and performance.

It is essential to recognize the importance of work-life balance, particularly for working mothers, in creating a healthy working environment and improving overall performance. Employers that prioritize work-life balance policies are better equipped to support their employees' well-being and improve performance. As such, work-life balance is a shared responsibility between employers and employees, with the aim of achieving an optimal balance between personal and job responsibilities (*Thevanes, N. & Mangaleswaran.T, 2018*).

The study of working mothers in non-profit organizations highlights various critical factors that impact work-life balance, such as personal, balancing, motivational, organizational, career advancement, and psychological factors. The study underscores the importance of establishing work-life balance that meets individual and family needs, leading to reduced stress and burnout, ultimately resulting in better job performance and employee commitment. Therefore, addressing work-life balance issues is essential to enhance job performance, employee well-being, and overall productivity (*Perez EF, Opulencia KY & Marpaung GP 2023*).

Therefore, work-life balance is critical for job performance, employee well-being, and organizational productivity. By prioritizing work-life balance policies, organizations can foster a positive workplace culture that supports employees' motivation, productivity, and performance.

6.2 Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. Organizations should continue to prioritize work-life balance policies that can enhance employees' well-being and improve job performance. By doing so, they can foster a positive workplace culture that supports employees' motivation, productivity, and performance.
2. The study shows that some working mothers need more personal time for their interests and well-being, which can reduce stress and burnout. Thus organizations should implement policies that support employees in achieving work-life balance and personal growth.
3. Organizations should explore ways to improve balancing and personal factors identified in the study and provide resources for employees to manage work and family responsibilities. Flexible timing and the possibility to work from home can also help in managing personal and professional responsibilities.
4. Career development support was found to be lacking for some working mothers. Therefore, organizations should provide opportunities for career advancement, training, and development to support their professional growth.

5. Childcare facilities and child care leave, personal leave for work-life balance, non-discrimination, and gender biases in promotional policies and decision making, effective communication of organizations policies need to be implemented to support working mothers' needs in the workplace.
6. Finally, both employers and employees have a shared responsibility to achieve an optimal balance between personal and job responsibilities. Organizations should encourage open communication with their employees to better understand their unique work-life balance needs.

By implementing these recommendations, organizations can prioritize work-life balance and support employees' well-being, ultimately leading to better job performance and employee commitment.

7.0 RECOMMENDATION FOR FURTHER STUDIES

Consideration should be given to the limitations of this study when interpreting the research findings. To explore this topic further, future research should be conducted in various cities beyond Yangon.

Additionally, while this study focused solely on working mothers in non-profit organizations, future research should explore work-life balance among working mothers in the private sector and extend to working parents in general.

Furthermore, to obtain more comprehensive findings, future studies can include additional variables such as family conflicts and challenges, job satisfaction and commitment, staff burnout, and turnover intentions.

To gain a deeper understanding of the factors that impact work-life balance for working mothers, researchers should consider including additional variables in future studies. This study's findings should be viewed in light of its limitations, including that it was conducted solely in Yangon city and focused on working mothers from non-profit organizations. Future research should expand to include working mothers in the private sector and extend to working parents more broadly. In addition, future studies can incorporate variables such as family conflicts and challenges, job satisfaction and commitment, staff burnout, and turnover intentions. These additional variables will yield more comprehensive findings for researchers.

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Appendix - Survey Questionnaire

Questionnaires for Impact of work-life balance of working mothers on job performance in Non-profit Sectors, in Yangon, Myanmar)

This questionnaire will be used only for a survey that will be conducted in a research required to submit for the attainment of my M0aster's Degree. The information you provide will remain confidential and will be used only for dissertation purpose only. So, I would like to request you to answer completely and truly.

Section (A): Demographic Profile

1. Age

- € Under 25
- € 25-34
- € 35-44
- € 45-54
- € 55 and above

2. Marital Status

- € Married life (with fully support from family)
- € Single Mother (without support of extended family)
- € Married life (with long distance relation with spouse)

3. Do you have children?

- € Yes
- € No

4. If you have the children please select

- € 1
- € 2
- € 3 and above

5. Working Organization

- € UN organization
- € INGO
- € LNGO

6. Professional sectors

- € Program staff (Operation , Program Management ,M&E ,Data Management ,etc)
- € Support service staff (Admin , HR, Finance , ICT , Logistics ,etc)

7. Monthly salary

- € Under MMK 500,000
- € MMK 500,000 – 1,000,000
- € MMK 1,000, – 2,000,000
- € MMK 2,000,000 – 3,000,000
- € Above MMK 3,000,000

8. Working Experience

- € Under 1 year
- € 1-3 years
- € 3-5 years
- € Above 5 years

9. Do you think work-life balance is a big impact to working mother's job performance?

€ Yes

€ No

Section (B): Work-life balance of working mother in Non-profit sectors (In Yangon, Myanmar)

Please rank the following on a scale 1-5 to reflect your feelings and the extent to which you agree with the statements. The minimum rank is 1 and the maximum rank is 5. Please circle or highlight the answer in bold.

	Personal Factors	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Sufficient time to take care of yourself (beauty and relax)	1	2	3	4	5
2	Enough time for friend gathering and travelling	1	2	3	4	5
3	Enough time to sleep and exercise	1	2	3	4	5
4	Spend time for personal hobby	1	2	3	4	5

	Balancing Factors	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Prioritize my job over my personal life	1	2	3	4	5
2	Sacrifice sleep and worry for work	1	2	3	4	5
3	Children showing the signs of distress due to lack of family time	1	2	3	4	5
4	Satisfied with working hours and it fits with my private life	1	2	3	4	5
5	Performance Time management is important for work life balance	1	2	3	4	5
6	Quality time with family	1	2	3	4	5

	Organizational Factors	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Support for maternity leave with pay programs	1	2	3	4	5
2	Support for Availability of childcare facilities at work	1	2	3	4	5
3	Non- discriminations to working mothers employee	1	2	3	4	5
4	Flexibility given by manager in fulfilling the maternal duties	1	2	3	4	5
5	Support of flextime policies	1	2	3	4	5
6	Provide leave to work life balance	1	2	3	4	5
7	Medical insurance policy for family	1	2	3	4	5

	Motivational Factors	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Personal passion and proud on job	1	2	3	4	5
2	Safe and comfortable working environments	1	2	3	4	5
3	Financial independence	1	2	3	4	5
4	Support from supervisors and colleagues at work	1	2	3	4	5
5	Support from family and environments	1	2	3	4	5

	Career Advancement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Provide training for personal development at work	1	2	3	4	5
2	Motherhood is hindering your career growth	1	2	3	4	5
3	Learning opportunity for latest trends of your job	1	2	3	4	5
4	Equality in Gender for Promotion	1	2	3	4	5

	Psychological factors	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Support of spouse for dual roles	1	2	3	4	5
2	Flexible working hours at work	1	2	3	4	5
3	Family support for dual life	1	2	3	4	5
4	Work pressure influence your peace of mind	1	2	3	4	5
5	Being a mother makes you less affordable as an employee	1	2	3	4	5